

Performance Evaluation of Multiport Y-Converters using Renewable Source Mission Profile

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Abstract—The integration of distributed energy resources (DERs) into electrical grids demands efficient dc–ac interfacing solutions. This work focuses on the design and optimization of converter topologies for such integration, particularly for interconnecting 400 V dc microgrids (MGs) with the European low-voltage ac grid. The Y-converter topology is investigated, offering single-stage power conversion and bidirectional buck–boost capability. Two design approaches are evaluated: employing separate two-port Y-converters (2Y) and utilizing a single, integrated multiport Y-converter (MPC). A Pareto optimization framework is applied to explore trade-offs between efficiency and power density, based on detailed analysis of component losses, volume, and design constraints. Results show that both approaches achieve high efficiency and power density, with the MPC exhibiting superior average efficiency for dc power transfer by avoiding additional losses introduced by the intermediate ac stage present in the 2Y configuration. These findings demonstrate the strong potential of MPCs as compact and efficient interfaces for future dc MGs integration with the ac grid.

Index Terms—dc microgrids, multiport converters, bidirectional buck-boost converter, pareto optimization, renewable energy.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rise of renewable energy is reshaping electrical grids, driven particularly by the increased adoption of distributed energy resources (DERs). Current efforts in the energy sector, led by researchers and policymakers, are focused on creating effective solutions to transition from traditional fossil-fuel-based power systems to green energy systems [1]. While traditional network reinforcement remains a viable option for increasing grid capacity, it presents critical drawbacks, such as high costs and long implementation times. In contrast, dc microgrids (MGs) have emerged as an effective solution for addressing local energy needs. These systems integrate distributed power sources directly into distribution networks and are highly compatible with renewable energy sources, modern electric loads, and energy storage systems [2].

As the adoption of dc MGs continues to grow, there is an increasing need to re-evaluate how these systems are efficiently interfaced with existing ac grids. Achieving high efficiency, compactness, and scalability is essential—especially as the number of interconnected dc MGs expands. Two main design strategies are considered, as illustrated in Fig. 1: deploying multiple two-port converters, each dedicated to a single dc MG, or utilizing a single multiport converter capable of simultaneously interfacing multiple dc MGs.

Fig. 1: ac grid integration of two dc MGs: (a) separate two-port converters vs. (b) multiport converter.

Given the motivations for adopting 400 V as the voltage level for residential dc MGs [3], this study focuses on interfacing a 400 V dc MG with the European low-voltage ac grid, which also operates at a 400 V line-to-line voltage. Buck-type rectifiers are particularly well-suited for this application, as they can directly step down the ac voltage to the dc level [4]. In contrast, boost-type converters—such as the two-level voltage source converter (VSC)—require an additional buck stage, increasing system complexity and reducing overall efficiency.

Among the various buck-type topologies reported in the literature, the Y-converter has demonstrated superior performance, as highlighted in [5], compared to other state-of-the-art solutions such as current source converters (CSCs) in both six-switch and seven-switch configurations [6], [7], as well as the Swiss converter [8]. The key advantages of the Y-converter include single-stage power conversion, bidirectional power flow, and buck-boost capability, which enables flexible energy transfer between the ac and dc sides. These features enhance its versatility across a wide range of applications.

Building on this foundation, the multiport structure, introduced in [9], extends the basic two-port Y-converter by incorporating additional dc ports. This advancement allows for the simultaneous integration of multiple dc sources and loads, significantly improving system-level flexibility and energy management. The topological schematics of the Y-converter and its multiport extension are illustrated in Fig. 2a and Fig. 2b, respectively.

Previous studies [5], [9] have demonstrated that the Y-

Fig. 2: Schematics of the evaluated topologies: (a) two port Y-converter; (b) multiport Y-converter (MPC).

converter and its multiport variant offer efficient integration of dc energy resources and effective energy management within dc MGs, while ensuring seamless interfacing with the ac grid.

This research focuses on optimizing a power electronic interface that connects two dc ports and one ac port. The main objectives are to achieve high efficiency—minimizing energy losses and operational costs—and to maximize power density for a compact design. Two design approaches are investigated and compared: the first utilizes a single multiport Y-converter, which consolidates multiple energy pathways into a unified converter unit; the second employs a dual Y-converter configuration, in which two independent Y-converters are used to achieve the same functionality.

The performance of both configurations is evaluated in terms of efficiency and power density under two application scenarios. The first scenario considers the interconnection of two 400 V dc MGs, where the nominal efficiency is assessed under full power operation at each port. The second scenario focuses on renewable energy integration, with a photovoltaic (PV) system connected to the first dc port and an energy storage system to the second. Here, the average efficiency is calculated over a realistic PV mission profile to evaluate

energy conversion performance under variable operating conditions.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Sec. II describes the multi-objective optimization (MOO) procedure, including component modeling and key design trade-offs. Sec. III outlines the methodology for mission-profile-based efficiency evaluation under dynamic renewable energy conditions. Sec. IV presents a comparative analysis of the results, focusing on efficiency, power density, and component-level losses and volume for both the MPC and 2Y configurations. Finally, Sec. V concludes the study and summarizes key findings.

II. MULTI-OBJECTIVE OPTIMIZATION PROCEDURE

The MOO provides a framework for systematically exploring inherent trade-offs in complex systems, such as power electronics converters, where competing performance metrics cannot be simultaneously optimized [10]. For example, increasing switching frequency (f_{sw}) may improve power density (reducing component size) but degrade efficiency due to higher switching and inductor losses. Traditional single-objective optimization risks suboptimal outcomes by prioritizing one performance metric at the expense of others. In contrast, MOO identifies Pareto-optimal solution designs where no further improvement can be achieved in one objective without affecting another, thereby preserving balance across performance indices [11].

This work employs MOO to design the power electronics converters under study. A flowchart of the MOO methodology highlighting design space exploration and Pareto front generation is presented in Fig. 3. The flowchart covers tunable parameters, component selections, and practical constraints. Efficiency and power density are selected as critical performance indices: efficiency governs energy savings, while power density determines compactness, a key driver in modern energy systems. Using the direct-search method, we generate the Pareto front (i.e., the set of non-dominated design solutions representing optimal compromises) between efficiency and power density.

The MOO procedure begins by defining the system specifications, including power ratings, voltage levels, and design constraints. Next, the modulation scheme, material datasets, and sweep parameters are selected. A comprehensive exploration of the design space is then carried out by varying tunable parameters and component choices. Each design iteration is evaluated to assess its impact on efficiency and power density—the two primary objectives used to identify the Pareto-optimal trade-off.

A. Component Modeling

Component modeling which is critical to the optimization framework is summarized below.

1) *Semiconductor Design*: The semiconductor loss model integrates time-varying current and voltage waveforms derived from steady-state analysis under the selected modulation. Conduction losses are computed as functions of the instantaneous

Fig. 3: Flowchart of the MOO methodology highlighting design space exploration and Pareto front generation.

current, average junction temperature (T_j), and temperature-dependent on-state resistance. Switching losses (E_{on} , E_{off}) are calculated using waveform data and experimentally obtained loss maps [12]. These losses feed into a thermal network model to iteratively compute T_j , accounting for junction-to-ambient thermal resistance and heatsink performance. This iterative coupling ensures accurate loss-volume trade-offs for semiconductors and heatsinks.

2) *Inductor Design*: The magnetic design methodology begins with a reluctance-based model that accounts for core nonlinearities, such as flux-dependent permeability, and air gap effects. Core losses are estimated using the improved-improved generalized Steinmetz equation (i^2 GSE, [13]), with operating-point-dependent Steinmetz coefficients extracted from experimentally derived loss maps. Winding losses are computed by accounting for both skin and proximity effects, with copper conductivity corrected for temperature variations. Finally, a thermal model is applied to predict the inductor's internal temperature distribution [14].

3) *Capacitor Design*: Capacitor designs are evaluated based on their losses, modeled via frequency- and temperature-dependent equivalent series resistance (ESR). The design space includes capacitor type (e.g., film, ceramic), rated capacitance, and voltage, enabling exploration of size-loss compromises.

III. MISSION-PROFILE EFFICIENCY CALCULATION METHODOLOGY

This section presents a methodology for computing the average efficiency of the multiport converter under a realistic photovoltaic mission profile, while maintaining low computational effort. The first step involves precomputing the converter's power-dependent losses at discrete operating points for Port-1 (P_{dc1}) and Port-2 (P_{dc2}). These points cover bidirectional power levels relative to each port's rated power ($P_{dc,rated1}$, $P_{dc,rated2}$):

$$\{P_{dc1}\} = \{-P_{dc,rated1}, -(P_{dc,rated1} - \Delta P_1), \dots, P_{dc,rated1}\} \quad (1)$$

$$\{P_{dc2}\} = \{-P_{dc,rated2}, -(P_{dc,rated2} - \Delta P_2), \dots, P_{dc,rated2}\} \quad (2)$$

where

$$\Delta P_1 = \frac{2P_{dc,rated1}}{N}, \quad \Delta P_2 = \frac{2P_{dc,rated2}}{M} \quad (3)$$

define the step sizes for N and M grid points. For instance, a 10-point grid for a 5 kW port yields: $-5, -4, \dots, 5$ kW. The resulting loss matrix Γ of dimensions $N \times M$ maps each (P_{dc1} , P_{dc2}) combination to its corresponding loss value. The 250-hour PV power profile shown in Fig. 5b, $P_{PV}(t)$, is used to compute the converter losses at each point of the PV profile. The ac port power P_{ac} is fixed as the time-averaged PV power:

$$P_{ac} = \frac{1}{250} \sum_{t=0}^{250} P_{PV}(t) \quad (4)$$

The storage port dynamically balances the system to ensure that the storage absorbs PV variability, maintaining constant P_{ac} despite fluctuating PV input, yielding

$$P_{storage}(t) = P_{PV}(t) - P_{ac} \quad (5)$$

For each timestep t , the converter's instantaneous loss $\Gamma(t)$ is estimated using a two-dimensional interpolation method

Fig. 4: Pareto-front evaluation of both designs considering nominal efficiency.

over the precomputed loss surface Γ at the corresponding operating points (P_{dc1}, P_{dc2}) :

$$\Gamma(t) = \Gamma(P_{dc1} = P_{PV}(t), P_{dc2} = P_{storage}(t)) \quad (6)$$

To evaluate average efficiency, the instantaneous operating power $P_{op}(t)$ is also defined as:

$$P_{op}(t) = \max(|P_{PV}(t)|, |P_{storage}(t)|, |P_{ac}|) \quad (7)$$

The average efficiency η_{avg} is then computed over the evaluated time span as:

$$\eta_{avg} = \frac{\sum_{t=0}^{250} P_{op}(t)}{\sum_{t=0}^{250} P_{op}(t) + \sum_{t=0}^{250} \Gamma(t)} \times 100\% \quad (8)$$

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fig.4 presents the η - ρ Pareto front for the investigated designs in case of dc MGs interconnection at nominal power conditions for each ports. The results highlight that low-frequency designs exhibit reduced power density due to the increased volume of magnetic components, whereas higher-frequency designs lead to lower efficiency. This behavior is consistent for both the MPC and the 2Y configurations. Both configurations achieve efficiencies exceeding 97.5% across the evaluated range, with peak efficiencies surpassing 98.5% at the maximum power-density points. Notably, the MPC demonstrates a slight advantage over the 2Y configuration, achieving higher power density for a given efficiency.

Fig.5a illustrates the mission profile, where a PV system is connected to dc port 1 and a storage system to dc port 2, while constant ac power is supplied to the grid. The resulting average efficiencies of both configurations under this profile are shown in Fig.5b. Even if both configurations achieve high efficiency, the MPC achieves an average efficiency of 96.8%, compared to 95.3% for the 2Y configuration at the power density limit—an improvement of 1.5%. This gain is primarily

Fig. 5: Mission-profile based evaluation of both configurations: (a) The Mission profile adopted in the evaluation; (b) Pareto-front evaluation of both designs considering average efficiency.

attributed to the MPC's capability to directly transfer power between dc ports, thereby reducing semiconductor losses in the ac stage. In contrast, the 2Y configuration incurs additional losses in the ac stage even during dc-dc power transfers.

The maximum power-density points of the MPC and 2Y designs in Fig.4 were chosen to conduct a detailed volume and loss breakdown analysis. Fig.6a illustrates the volume distribution, where ac capacitors dominate (31.5% for MPC and 36.6% for 2Y), followed by inductors (31.1% for MPC and 21.8% for 2Y) and semiconductor components. The ac-line filter's inductors are not included in the comparison between the MPC and 2Y design concepts.

At the same time, Fig.6b breaks down losses for both designs, revealing lower total losses in the MPC. The primary contributors are core and copper losses in inductors, followed by conduction losses in boost-side semiconductors and buck-side semiconductor losses. Fig.6c analyzes the designs under dc-dc power transfer conditions, with corresponding losses detailed. The MPC design concept enables direct dc-dc power transfer, eliminating ac-side losses and achieving total losses of 106.2 W. In contrast, the 2Y design lacks a direct dc path,

Fig. 6: (a) Components' volume distribution at the maximum power-density points. (b) Power loss distribution across converter components at the maximum power-density points. (c) dc-dc power transfer loss comparison between MPC and 2Y topologies

incurring additional buck-side semiconductor losses resulting in a total losses of 143.1 W, a 34.7% increase compared to the MPC. This difference highlights the efficiency benefit of direct power transfer in the MPC.

Fig. 7 shows the loss and volume distribution for the Pareto-optimal design solutions generated by the MOO presented in Fig. 4, in which the trade-off between nominal efficiency and power density is shown as a Pareto front and each point along the curves represents an optimized design found for a specific switching frequency, which is color defined. Fig. 7 fur-

ther details the internal component-wise distribution of losses and volume for these designs at their respective operating frequencies. Fig. 7a show the percentage distribution of power losses among components for the pareto front MPC and 2Y converter designs, respectively, as a function of switching frequency. The x-axis spans from 60 kHz to 120 kHz. For each frequency, the plots shows on y-axis the percentage share of each component's loss to the total power loss in the corresponding optimized design.

The stacked areas indicate that at lower frequencies, dominant losses results from inductor iron losses (P_{fe}), copper losses (P_{cu}), and semiconductor conduction losses (P_{cond}). As the switching frequency increases, the percentage contribution from semiconductor switching losses (P_{sw}), in both buck and boost stages, increase.

Fig. 7b shows the percentage distribution of volume among components for the pareto front MPC and 2Y designs across the switching frequency range of 60 kHz to 120 kHz. The x-axis represents the switching frequency, while the y-axis represents each component's share of the total volume for the corresponding optimized design.

The stacked areas shows that, at lower frequencies, inductors occupy the largest share of volume. As the frequency increases, the volume share of inductors decreases sharply. In contrast, other components such as semiconductors, buck and boost sides' elements (including heatsinks), and both dc and ac capacitors contribute a larger percentage to the total volume.

V. CONCLUSION

This research highlights the optimization of multiport Y-converter solutions to interface two dc ports and an ac port using a single converter. By focusing on the Y-converter and its multiport extension, the study demonstrates the potential of these topologies to achieve high efficiency and power density.

The multiport Y-converter and the two separate Y-converter configuration were systematically analyzed using a multi-objective optimization framework. The results reveal that both configurations can achieve knee solutions with efficiencies exceeding 98.5% at power densities higher than 10 kW/dm³. However, the MPC exhibits better performance in terms of power density for a given efficiency. Furthermore, the MPC demonstrated enhanced average efficiency performance during power transfer between dc ports due to the elimination of losses on the ac side.

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Fig. 7: Distribution of (a) losses and (b) volume for the evaluated converter designs.

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